

PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL MANAGEMENT - A MOTIVATION TO EMPLOYEE

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Abstract:

Human resource managers have traditionally accorded employee performance as a prime focus. As a result, several performance appraisal techniques have been devised to help establish employee performance. In contemporary times, performance appraisals have been extended beyond rating the employee's performance to aspects such as motivation. Accordingly, this study sought to investigate the effectiveness of performance appraisal systems and their effect on employee motivation. The study's primary objectives pertained to establishing the moderating role of performance appraisal as a motivation tool and potential challenges. The study findings show significant positive outcomes when the organization uses performance appraisal as a motivation tool. Further, the study finds that more than one appraisal technique helps yield greater satisfaction and, consequently, higher motivational levels. The specific aspects of performance appraisal systems (PAS) that help improve motivation include linking performance to rewards, using the PAS to help set objectives and benchmarks, and using PA to help identify employees' strengths and weaknesses.

Key Words: Performance, Appraisal, Motivation, Employee.

Introduction:

Performance appraisal is a widely discussed concept in the field of performance management. The importance of performance appraisal systems partly arises from the nature of the current business environment, which is marked by the need to achieve organizational goals and remain relevant in intensely competitive markets through superior employee performance. Within this context, various studies suggest that organizations can hardly control the behaviour of their employees. The organizations can however control how employees perform their jobs. In addition, performance management research shows that a significant number of employees tend to have the desire to serve their jobs well as part of their individual goals and a demonstration of loyalty towards the organization. Arguably, the key to ensuring that employees perform well lies in the ability to provide them with the proper working environment. Such an environment generally includes fair treatment, support, effective communication, and collaboration. According to experts, these qualities are created by an effective performance appraisal system.

Objective of the Study:

- To establish and explore the link between performance appraisal and employee motivation.
- To analyze the types of performance appraisal, motivation, and their effectiveness

Scope of the Study:

- To analyze the Performances Appraisal procedures (PA)
- To study the effectiveness of Performances Appraisal
- To know employee opinions about Performances Appraisal
- To understand the transformation of performance appraisal from traditional to modern
- To get an insight into the relative importance of performance appraisal in an organization

Methodology of the Study:

The research design adopted for the study is Explorative & Conclusive research design. A Questionnaire with 40 questions was designed to capture employees' raw data and responses. Nearly 90 random employees in managerial positions were chosen as a sample for data collection in the study.

Tools Involved:

Quantitative data obtained from the questionnaire responses were analyzed through the use of statistical packages, namely

- Simple Percentage analysis
- Chi-Square test

Period of Study:

The time period of study was from (1.03.2022) to (4.05.2022). Two months period is taken for this study on Performance Appraisal with Reference to employees in HDFC Bank.

Type of Sampling:

The simple Random sampling technique made it possible for respondents of varying ages, gender, experience, and other demographics to participate in the study. The reason for choosing this sampling technique is to achieve an unbiased, conclusive, and more representative outcome at the end of the study.

Simple Percentage Analysis:

Age:

Less than 30	23	26%
30-40	38	42%
40-50	21	23%
50 & above	8	9%
Total	90	100%

Out of 90 employees under study, it is depicted that 38(42%) employees age is between 30-40, remaining 23(26%) are less than 30 and 21(23%) employees age is between 40-50 and 8(9%) employees are 50 & above.

Gender:

Male	45	50%
Female	45	50%
Total	90	100%

Out of 90 employees under study, it is depicted that 45(50%) employees are male and 45(50%) employees are female. (Equal number of male and female)

Position:

Branch Manager	9	10%
Relationship Manager	9	10%
Accountant	16	18%
Finance Manager	14	16%
Investment Banker	13	14%
Bank Teller	11	12%
Other	18	20%
Total	90	100%

Out of 90 employees under study, it depicted that 18(20%) employees are in other position like Credit Manager, Sales Manager, Account Executive, Loan Processor, Welcome Desk, etc., 16(18%) are Accountant, 14(16%) are Finance Manager, 13(14%) are Investment Banker, 11(12%) are Bank Teller, 9(10%) are Relationship Manager and 9(10%) are Branch Manager.

Experience:

Below 5 years	34	38%
5-10 years	38	42%
Above 10	18	20%
Total	90	100%

Out of 90 employees under study, it is depicted that 38(44%) employees experience is between 5 to 10 years, 34(38%) employees experience is below 5 years and 18(20%) employees experience is above 10.

Interaction with Upper Level Management:

Daily	36	40%
Weekly	24	27%
Rarely	30	33%
Total	90	100%

Out of 90 employees under study, it is depicted that 36(40%) employees are daily interacting with their upper level management, 30(33%) employees are interacting rarely with their upper level management and 24(27%) employees are weekly interacting with their upper level management.

Period of Performance Appraisal:

Quarterly	52	58%
Yearly	38	42%
Total	90	100%

Out of 90 employees under study, it is depicted that 52(58%) employees period of Performance Appraisal is Quarterly and remaining all 38(42%) employees period of Performance Appraisal is yearly.

Objective of Performance Appraisal:

Promotion	69	44%
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Training	22	14%
Incentives	54	34%
Other	12	8%
Total	157	100%

Out of 90 employees under study, Objective of Performance Appraisal is depicted that, 69(44%) for promotion, 54(34%) for incentives, 22(14%) for training and 12(8%) for other.

Performance Appraisal are Related To:

Retention of employees	27	27%
Recruitment System	17	17%
Development of employees	41	41%
All of these	15	15%
Total	100	100%

Out of 90 employees under study, Performance Appraisal is depicted that, 41(41%) for Development of employees, 27(27%) for retention of employees, 17(17%) for recruitment system and 15(15%) for all of these.

Parameter of Appraisal:

Defining Goals	16	14%
Training & Development	23	20%
Documentation	10	9%
Reward & Recognition	64	57%
Total	113	100%

Out of 90 employees under study, Parameter of Appraisal is depicted that, 64(57%) for Reward & Recognition, 23(20%) for Training & Development, 16(14%) for Defining Goals and 10(9%) for Documentation.

Technique in Performance Appraisal:

Ranking Method	46	51%
Check List Method	44	49%
Total	90	100%

Out of 90 employees under study, it is depicted that 46(51%) employees Appraisal technique is Ranking method and 44(49%) employees Appraisal technique is Check List method.

Period of Performance Appraisal Received:

Last 6 months	57	63%
Last 12 months	33	37%
Total	90	100%

Out of 90 employees under study, it is depicted that 57(63%) employees Performance Appraisal Period is last 6 month and 33(37%) employees Performance Appraisal Period is last 12 months.

Chi-square Test:

Technique of PA and Period of PA:

Ha - There is an association between techniques and period of performance appraisal received
 Ho - There is no association between techniques and period of performance appraisal received

Technique of (PA)	Period of (PA)		Total
	46	57	
	44	33	77
Total	90	90	180

Calculated value = 2.52 Level of significant = 0.05 Table value = 3.84
 Ho is True. There is no association between techniques and period of performance appraisal received

Parameter and Objective of Performance Appraisal:

Ha – There is an association between parameter and objective of performance appraisal
 Ho - There is no association between parameter and objective of performance appraisal

Objective of (PA)	Parameter of (PA)		Total
	69	16	
	22	23	
	54	10	
	12	64	76
Total	157	113	270

Calculated value = 94.23 Level of significant = 0.05 Table value = 7.81
 Ha is True. There is an association between parameter and objective of performance appraisal

Experience and Interaction with Upper Level Management:

Ha – There is an association between experience and Interaction with upper level management
 Ho - There is no association between experience and Interaction with upper level management

Experience	Interaction with Upper Level Management		Total
		34	36
	38	24	62
	18	30	48
Total	90	90	180

Calculated Value: 6.216 Level of significant = 0.05 Table value = 5.99

Ha is True. There is an association between experience and Interaction with upper level management

Conclusion:

Every employee in an organization increases the productivity and goodwill of every company. An employee, being an individual, is treated as an asset in the organization. So the organization should mainly emphasize performance appraisal techniques and its development program. Both the appraiser and appraisee should realize the principle and use the tool of the appraisal system in a constructive way for the prosperity of the organization. The performance appraisal technique prevailing in the organization is fair. Employees are satisfied with the present performance appraisal system, a traditional one. As many new appraisal techniques emerge, the organization can implement a modern technique that would be more effective.

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